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The Improvement of Selected Soil Chemical Properties Using Singapore Daisy Based Compost in Ultisols

Author's Details:

^{1*}Zainal Mukhtar, ²Nanik Setyowati and ³Eka Wiyanti

¹Department of Soil Science, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Bengkulu, Indonesia

²Department of Crop Production, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Bengkulu, Indonesia

³Agroecotechnology Study Program, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Bengkulu, Indonesia

*Corresponding Author: muktamar@unib.ac.id

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Abstract

An acid soil such as Ultisols is the potential for the improvement of crop productivity by the application of organic fertilizer. This research aimed to compare selected chemical properties of Ultisols as affected by Singapore daisy compost at a different time of application. The study took place at the Screen House in Pasar Melintang Village, City of Bengkulu, Indonesia, 14 m above sea level, assigning Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with two factors. The factors were Singapore daisy compost time of application, including one week before planting (WBP), 2 WBP, and at planting (AP), and the rate of the compost ranging from 0 to 10, 20, and 30 tons/ha. The application of Singapore daisy compost two weeks before planting exhibited the highest total soil nitrogen of Ultisols. The Singapore daisy compost at rates of 20-30 tons/ha significantly increased the chemical properties of Ultisols.

Keywords: compost, soil properties, Ultisol, *Wedelia trilobata*

Introduction

Ultisols make up the majority of the soil types in Bengkulu Province, Indonesia. Hardjowigeno (2003) describes Ultisols as soil with an acidic argillic horizon, high acidity, low base saturation, and high Al content. The high Al concentration in Ultisol often causes phosphate fixation. An extensive leaching process in Ultisols causes the depleted nitrogen content. Fertilization is necessary to improve the fertility of this soil.

The addition of organic matter is a way to increase soil fertility. Organic matter is a key component of soil fertility in terms of both physical and chemical properties and soil biology (Sasra, 2010). Organic matter application can improve the stability of soil aggregates, soil water holding capacity, cation exchange capacity (CEC), and reduce nutrient leaching.

According to Arbiwati (2000), organic matter applied to the soil has a positive effect. It can increase humus content, avoid environmental pollution, reduce the rate of nutrient loss due to erosion, and improve soil properties. The influence of organic matter on soil chemical fertility includes cation exchange capacity, anion exchange capacity, soil pH, soil buffering capacity, and soil nutrients. The addition of organic matter raises the negative charge, thereby increasing the cation exchange capacity (CEC). The addition of 10 tons/ha of straw to Ultisols increased soil CEC by 15.18% (Cahyani, 1996). With the addition of organic matter, the pH of the soil will rise.

Cahyani (1996) reported that adding organic matter to Ultisols increased soil pH while decreasing exchangeable Al. The exchangeable Al of Ultisols lowered from 3.65 me/100 g to 2.0 me /100 g by applying 25 tons/ha of manure (Muktamar et al., 1998). When comparing 35 ton/ha fertilization to control, there was a 5% increase in pH. Application of water hyacinth compost to Ultisols increased organic C after two weeks of incubation and the end of the plant vegetative period (Sitepu, 2009).

Compost is a source of organic matter for the soil, derived from the decomposition of living things' debris (plants and animals). Previous studies confirmed that compost released plant nutrients such as N, P, K and improved plant growth (Muir et al., 2010; Griffin and Hutchinson, 2007; Duong et al., 2012).

Released nutrients from the compost will eventually be available for the plant. However, compost is low in nutrients compared to synthetic fertilizers, but it can increase soil fertility when used in large

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quantities. Thus, compost can substitute for synthetic fertilizers. After three months, the application of Bermuda Grass compost can increase organic matter, C, P, Ca, and S. (Wright *et al.*, 2007). Muir *et al.* (2010) confirmed that fertilizing crops with Bermuda Grass compost increased crop yields by 15% at a dose of 36 tons/ha. Compared to synthetic fertilizers, compost and vermicompost can improve soil properties by increasing pH, organic matter, and nutrient content (Jouquet *et al.*, 2011). D'hose *et al.* (2012) also concluded that continuous application of compost improved N availability. Despite the low N-release, compost promotes the growth of vegetable crops.

Compost is composed of organic materials like plants, animals, and organic waste. Compostable materials include straw, shrubs, legumes, husks, and sawn wood. Furthermore, a lot of weeds are potential sources of compost. Singapore daisy (*Wedelia trilobata* L.) is a broad-leaf weed capable of providing organic matter (Setyowati *et al.*, 2009; Setyowati *et al.*, 2014a; Setyowati *et al.*, 2014b).

Handayani and Prawito (2006) reported that Singapore daisy has the potential as a source of organic fertilizer for short-term land improvement. According to Setyowati *et al.* (2009), Singapore daisy bokashi application increases C-organic, moisture, and soil pH. The highest yield of chili pepper was obtained using *Wedelia* compost and Siam weeds at a rate of up to 20 tons/ha, indicating that this organic fertilizer can substitute nitrogen fertilizer (Setyowati *et al.*, 2014a).

Excessive use of chemical fertilizers will deteriorate soil chemical, physical and biological properties. Compost application is a solution for restoring soil fertility. Compost primarily functions as an organic matter source to improve the soil's physical, biological, and chemical properties, leading to the improvement of crop production. This study aimed to compare selected chemical properties of Ultisols at different rates of Singapore daisy compost and application times.

Materials and Methods

Experimental Design

A greenhouse experiment was carried out in Pasar Melintang, City of Bengkulu, at 14 m above sea level. The experiment employed a Completely Randomized Design with two factors and five replications. The factors included the application time of Singapore daisy compost consisted of a week before planting (WBP), 2 WBP, and at the planting, and the compost rates were 0, 10, 20, and 30 tons/ha.

Soil Sampling and Compost Preparation

A soil sample was collected from Pasar Melintang Village at the depth of 0-20 cm. The soil was classified as Ultisols. The sample was air-dried and sieved with a 2 mm screen. A portion of the sample was sieved with a 0.5 mm screen and analyzed for an initial characterization of the soil, including pH, organic C, total N, available P, exchangeable K, exchangeable Al, CEC, and soil texture.

Compost was prepared: Singapore daisy (SD) weeds were chopped into approximately 4 cm pieces. The EM-4 solution was applied to the chopped weeds using a Knapsack sprayer. Compost material was then stacked on tiles and covered with clear plastic. The material was incubated for four weeks. The compost pile was turned over to ensure the supply of oxygen. Ripe compost was distinguished by its dark color, which indicates that it was ready for use. The compost was analyzed for pH and content of carbon (C), nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K).

Greenhouse Experiment

The experiment started with the preparation of growing media for tomatoes. According to the treatment, ten kg of soil sample was incorporated with compost and placed in a polybag. One-month-old tomato seedling was transplanted to the polybag. The soil sample was maintained moist during the experiment by watering when required. After harvesting, a soil sample was air-dried, sieved with 0.5 mm screen and analyzed for C-organic using Walky and Black Method. The pH at 1:1 ratio of sample and distilled water was measured using pH meter, N-total using Kjeldahl method, P-available using P-Bray I, exchangeable K using Flamephotometer after extraction 1N ammonium acetate, and exchangeable Al using titration method after extraction using 1N KCl.

Data analysis

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The data were analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) at a confidence level of 95%. The Polynomial Orthogonal Test (POT) at 5% was assigned to determine the compost rate treatment effect.

Results and Discussion

Except for N-total, Singapore daisy compost application times had no significant effect on all observed variables. In contrast, the compost rate significantly affected all variables but exchangeable Al. There was an interaction effect of the time of application and the compost rate on total soil nitrogen, as indicated in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of analysis of variance

Variables	Application time	Rate	Interaction
Soil pH	2,49 ^{ns}	12,71 ^{**}	2,07 ^{ns}
Total-N	196,77 ^{**}	200,64 ^{**}	28,55 ^{**}
P ₂ O ₅ available	3,18 ^{ns}	20,09 ^{**}	2,27 ^{ns}
Exch. K	2,52 ^{ns}	30,54 ^{**}	0,76 ^{ns}
Organic-C	1,87 ^{ns}	5,10 ^{**}	0,70 ^{ns}
Exch. Al	0,49 ^{ns}	5,85 ^{ns}	2,33 ^{ns}

Note: ns = not significantly different, * = significant different, ** = highly significant different

Effect of Application Time and Compost Rates on Soil Properties

Table 2 shows selected soil properties as affected by compost application time.

Table 2. Effect of compost application time on soil properties

	Selected Soil Properties					
	pH (H ₂ O)	N-Total (%)	P ₂ O ₅ (ppm)	Exch-K (me/100g)	C-org (%)	Exch-Al (me/100g)
P ₁	4,10	0,20a	18,14	0,11	2,65	3,19
P ₂	4,07	0,19b	18,12	0,12	2,94	2,55
P ₃	3,95	0,13c	21,41	0,12	2,73	2,50

Note: numbers followed by the same letters at the same column are not significantly different at DMRT (5%). P₁ = 2 weeks before planting; P₂ = 1 weeks before planting; P₃ = at planting date.

The compost application time of 2 weeks before planting (WBP) produced the highest total N (0.20%). The highest total-N at 2 WBP indicated that the release of N from organic matter decomposition did take time. The initial soil analysis showed a total N content of 0.12%. The availability of total soil N after harvesting increased by 53.84%. The addition of Singapore daisy compost at 1 WBP and at planting increased the total N content of the soil in comparison to the initial soil conditions. The total nitrogen content of composted soil at 1 WBP was 0.19% and 0.13% at planting (Table 2). According to Rochani (2001), the addition of Azolla sp compost can increase organic matter in the soil, improve the physical and chemical properties of the soil, and make the soil more friable, allowing oxygen, water, and minerals to move freely. Additionally, Azolla sp will degrade into simpler chemicals more rapidly.

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Figure 1. The effect of compost rate on organic-C

The application time of compost did not affect soil P and K, organic-C, and exchangeable Al. The compost rates, on the other hand, affected the soil properties. An increasing compost rate resulted in significant effects on all selected soil properties observed in the experiment.

Increased compost rate resulted in a significant increase in soil organic carbon (Figure 1). Compost rate yielded a positive linear response in orthogonal polynomial analysis on C-organic. A 30 tons/ha compost application increased soil organic C by 120.90% compared to the control. Total organic-C continues to rise as the rate of Singapore daisy compost increases.

The findings of this study were in line with the observations by Syukur, and Indah (2006), where applying compost and manure to the soil increased the C-organic content. The higher organic fertilizer application resulted in higher C-organic content of the soil. This result is associated with the carbon content of the compost. A previous study confirmed that compost increased organic-C of the soil (Muktamar *et al.*, 2016)

Figure 2. Effect of Singapore daisy compost on the soil pH

As illustrated in Figure 2, increasing the compost rate linearly increases the soil pH. Compost application at a rate of 30 tons/ha raised soil pH to 4.2 compared to the control. The addition of organic matter decreases soil pH since the decomposition process releases organic acids, such as humic and fulvic acids (Muktamar *et al.*, 2017), leading to a decrease in soil pH. However, if applied to acidic soil with a high Al content, it increases soil pH. The organic acids produced during decomposition covalently bonds Al to form complex compounds (chelates) (Spark, 2003), preventing Al hydrolysis and lowering proton production. As a result, the soil pH increased. A similar result is reported by Sianturi *et al.* (2019) where the application of organic fertilizer increased soil pH by as much as 15% after the addition of 20 ton/ha solid organic fertilizer.

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Sugito *et al.* (1995) reported that compost could improve pH and soil cation exchange cations (CEC). According to Wahyudin (2010), applying 30 tons/ha of cocoa husk bokashi can improve soil chemical properties such as pH by increasing the amount of organic matter in the soil. Cow manure can improve soil pH and reduce Al toxicity in plants (Muktamar *et al.*, 1998). Singapore daisy compost also affects the P₂O₅ content in the soil (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The concentration of P₂O₅ as affected by Singapore daisy compost

The application of compost at different rates produced a quadratic response with the equation $y = -0.0173x^2 + 0.9127x + 11.639$ ($R^2 = 0.8913$) to the P₂O₅. The content of P₂O₅ in the soil fertilized with compost of 30 tons/ha was 23,667 ppm with an optimum 26.4 tons/ha rate. At higher rates of Singapore daisy compost, P₂O₅ was not significantly affected (leveling off).

Compost affects the availability of P in the soil both directly and indirectly through the activity of organic acids produced during compost decomposition, which helps release P fixed by Al, and insoluble Fe becomes soluble (Lukistasari *et al.*, 2015). The higher the organic matter rate, the higher the concentration of N, P, and K in the soil, which will play an essential role in plant metabolism (Pujisiswanto and Pangaribuan, 2008). According to Sanhua (2010), P is necessary for growth and fruit production.

Figure 4. Effect of compost on exchangeable K. Similar to P₂O₅, exchangeable K exhibited a quadratic response to compost application (Figure 4). Exchangeable K increased as the higher compost rate increased to 20 tons ha⁻¹, then the increase is level off afterward. The nutrient increased by 114.3% as the rate increased to 30 tons ha⁻¹ compared to control. A previous study noted that soil exchangeable K increased at higher rates of water hyacinth compost (Muktamar *et al.*, 2016).

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Figure 5. Relationship between compost dose and soil N

Total soil nitrogen has a similar trend to exchangeable K, where the response of this variable to compost application was quadratic (Figure 5). The availability of nitrogen in the soil is critical for plants. Total soil nitrogen increased by 69% as the compost rate increased from 0 to 30 tons/ha. The soil nitrogen significantly increased from 0 to 20 tons/ha; then the increase was level off afterward. Organic matter in soil undergoes decomposition, releasing nitrogen to the soil. As the rate of compost increases, released nitrogen to the soil also increases.

Furthermore, nitrogen is a component of compounds used within plant metabolism (Gardner *et al.*, 1991). Nitrogen is required by plants, particularly for vegetative growth and protein synthesis. Organic fertilizer releases nitrogen slowly, causing the availability to plant needs sometimes. According to Mukhtar *et al.* (2020), total soil nitrogen significantly increased since week 4 to 7 of organic fertilizer decomposition, indicating that availability of N needs four weeks after application.

The Interaction Effect of Application Time and Compost Dosage on Soil Chemical Properties.

The availability of nitrogen in the soil is also affected by the pH of the soil. Soil pH affects accelerating organic matter decomposition and releasing N for plant growth. Compost application at a 30 tons/ha rate is the best rate for N availability.

Figure 6. Effect of application time and compost dose on total soil N

Figure 6 shows that the time of application at planting time and 1 WBP produced a positive linear pattern to soil total-N. In contrast, the time of application of 2 WBP had a quadratic pattern. According to Figure 6, the highest total N was 0.25 percent when compost was applied 1 WBP and 2 WBP at a rate of 30 tons/Ha.

A higher application of organic matter released higher N in the soil. According to the findings of Abbasi *et al.* (2012), the application of wood ash and compost increased the mineralization of organic N in the soil by releasing nitrogen at rates of 48.5 and 76.1 mg N/kg, respectively.

Conclusions

1. Application of Singapore daisy compost two weeks before planting tomato provided the greatest improvement of total nitrogen in Ultisols.
2. A Singapore daisy compost at a rate of 20-30 tons/ha significantly improves the chemical properties of Ultisols as indicated by the improvement of organic-C, total-N, exchangeable K, available P, and soil pH.

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